

From policy to practice: The FAIR Action plan

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Brief summary: Many organisations endorse the FAIR principles, yet implementation in the Dutch Social Sciences and Humanities lags behind. This blogpost introduces the Action Plan towards FAIR Implementation, which identifies five bottlenecks and pairs them with five actionable solutions: Map, Equip, Reward, Train, Share.

This blogpost is a follow-up to the blogpost published on October 21 2025 ([FAIR Implementation Needs Community Engagement - ODISSEI – Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations](#))

Ambition alone is not enough

Many organisations, from universities to institutes, have signed up for FAIR principles and FAIRification. It is no secret why; making data FAIR reduces costs ([Cordis, 2023](#)), increases collaboration between researchers, enables future research and strengthens societal trust in research.

However, actual implementation of the FAIR principles still lags behind substantially and the gap between accepted high-level policies and everyday practices in SSH

(Social sciences and humanities) is considerable. This is due to a mix of technical and organisational hurdles: missing semantic resources, unclear roles and responsibilities, and a persistent lack of recognition for data-related work. Many researchers see little incentive to invest in FAIRification when data and software outputs receive far less acknowledgment than traditional publications.

This is where the **Action plan** comes in. Developed via the NWO-funded “Untangling FAIR Implementation in the Dutch SSH” project, its focus is on the practical realities of data stewards, researchers, repository managers, and policy officers.

What makes this any different from other action plans and initiatives to integrate FAIR principles into research? The difference here is that the FAIR action plan was built by the community for the community. In September 2025, a writing sprint took place where the community co-created parts of the document so that recommendations would reflect the realities of those that actually work with data and ensure strong community ownership. The action plan also more generally incorporated insights from stakeholders across the Dutch SSH ecosystem, including researchers, data stewards, infrastructure providers, and policymakers.

Core of the plan - Five bottlenecks, five actions

The Action Plan identifies 5 bottlenecks that impede FAIRification:

- Unclear responsibilities
- Insufficient data infrastructure
- Lack of reward and incentive
- Skill gaps
- Fragmented coordination

The Action Plan pairs each of these bottlenecks with a concrete action area and recommendations. Here's how the five challenges translate into five solutions.

1. From unclear responsibilities → MAP

One of the most frequently mentioned obstacles is simple: no one knows who is supposed to do what when it comes to FAIR data. Researchers assume support staff handle it; support staff assume researchers should do most of the work; while institutions assume it's someone else's problem. To fix this, the plan calls for a **MAP** of

both data flows and roles. The goal is clear organisational blueprints that define responsibilities for data management across the entire research lifecycle.

2. From insufficient infrastructure → **EQUIP**

Even when people want to make data FAIR, the technical tools often aren't there. Missing semantic resources, incompatible repositories, and fragmented systems make meaningful annotation and interoperability nearly impossible. The response is to **EQUIP**, invest in and improve digital infrastructures so that FAIRification becomes feasible and straightforward.

3. From lack of incentives → **REWARD**

Making data FAIR takes time and effort, but currently, that effort rarely shows up in hiring, promotion, or funding decisions. Researchers are not oblivious, they work toward what gets recognised. The plan's **REWARD** action area pushes institutions to embed FAIR criteria directly into research evaluation and recognition, from annual reviews to software showcases.

4. From skill gaps → **TRAIN**

Many researchers and support staff simply never learned how to apply FAIR principles in practice. They might want to do so, but lack the skills that are required. The **TRAIN** action area focuses on embedding FAIR skills into higher education curricula as a standard part of SSH training pathways, not just a one time workshop.

5. From fragmented coordination → **SHARE**

Finally, even when individual teams or departments succeed at FAIR, that knowledge stays local. There is no systematic way to share what works and what doesn't. The **SHARE** action area aims to foster ongoing collaboration and knowledge exchange across institutions to turn FAIR principles into community-wide practices.

This is only a brief overview. The full Action Plan and a one-page summary are both available on Zenodo [here](#).

Future action

This action plan is not supposed to be a standalone document and strategy, but rather a complement to already existing initiatives such as the [TDCC - SSH Roadmap](#) and the [SSH Sector Plan](#) by translating these broader ambitions into concrete steps that research institutions and stakeholders can take to improve FAIRification.

Please reach out to fairsupport@odissei-data.nl if you have ideas on how to implement any of the recommendations in your own institute!

Relevant links

- Full text of the Action Plan: <https://zenodo.org/records/19128135>
- <https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/444085-fairification-of-valuable-data-sets-to-share-the-wealth>

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Titel

Veel organisaties onderschrijven de FAIR-principes, maar de implementatie blijft achter. Vooral in de Sociale en Geesteswetenschappen (SSH) is de kloof tussen beleidsambities en dagelijkse praktijk groot. Denk aan technische knelpunten, onduidelijke verantwoordelijkheden, gebrek aan erkenning en weinig prikkels voor onderzoekers.

Om deze kloof te overbruggen, is er een praktisch en gemeenschappelijk gedreven actieplan ontwikkeld. Het plan identificeert vijf knelpunten en koppelt deze aan vijf actiegebieden: Map, Equip, Reward, Train en Share. Wat dit plan bijzonder maakt? Het is samen met de gemeenschap ontwikkeld – van onderzoekers tot data stewards en beleidsmakers.

Button: Lees hier meer (Link to english version)

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